

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-13-IG-2% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	13	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 13
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/19/2022 10:56:45 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 4:03:45 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.413	76712	7.12	8447
2	6.862	455631	42.30	40666
3	7.846	464532	43.12	38192
4	10.573	80328	7.46	4693

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-12-IG-2% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221119
Vial:	3	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 12
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/19/2022 9:16:13 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 4:05:00 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.362	201084	2.07	22258
2	6.732	9399545	96.99	849302
3	7.734	47959	0.49	3679
4	10.254	42744	0.44	2707